

INFLUENCE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON STUDENT AUTONOMY IN ESP COURSE ON THE CASE OF FERGANA STATE UNIVERSITY

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Introduction

The relevance of autonomy in language learning has received much attention lately owing to emerging paradigm designs in learning. Student autonomy means that the learners take sole responsibility for their learning processes and this is important for the acquisition of a second language since the learners are on their own. Many argue that self-directed learners or a self-directed learning process produces more engaged self-directed learners to whom learning tasks are more motivating and relevant as they are closer to real-life language use. Regarding the development of ESP courses at Fergana State University, it is important to discuss not only the benefits but also the absolute necessity of autonomy for preparing students for the internationalized labor market that is defined by predominantly English.

In this paper, it is argued that as AI technologies are extending the array of revolutionary instruments in the educational sphere, their influence on student self-governance cannot be dismissed. The self-paced teaching systems like the adaptive learning system, feedback systems, or intelligent tutored systems have opportunities that learner autonomy can benefit from through the delivery of learner conducive environment. However, the admission of AI in language education has brought some concern in terms of efficiency and also concerning its capacity to allow students to transform into independent learners. This study seeks to resolve the current problem of the impact of AI technology on the independence of students in ESP courses at Fergana State University, to contribute towards useful recommendations that can help enhance other strategies and techniques. This knowledge is valuable because it both expands the current theory base and has application for professors who need to foster language development within English as a second language students in the context of escalating digital learning environments.

2. Literature review

The study, which was done by Ahmad, was devoted to exploring the integration of AI for language learning in university students in China, Chinese pre-service teachers, and students in other European countries [1, p. 19]. In the results of the research, he says that AI influences the learning process by providing tailored content for each student according to his/her characteristics and knowledge level. It is real-time, getting practice, and incentive with game characteristics and the virtual assistants. As per the AI characteristics, learning outcomes are successfully associated with motivation, self-efficiency, and autonomy making a virtuous circle between the student and the learning process [1, pp.22-23].

In his research study, Erito surveyed 40 ESP practitioners teaching in eleven Universities, and the Higher School of Management, Tlemcen to find out the ESP practitioners' perception of the new emerging AI technology integration into ESP classrooms [2, pp.83-84]. The majority of the teachers in this study hold a positive impression of AI in ESP as they believe that it can boost their position and be helpful to learners' acquisition of language. While some teachers insist that online learning through applications of AI is a good idea, others worry about negatively affecting the learner's attentiveness and motivation due to excess reliance on technology. Most of the

teachers (80%) said that future technical training and support regarding the use of AI in the classroom is essential, and they also want funds to buy AI tools and applications [2, p. 88].

Zamanpour and Etemadzadeh examined the effect of AI-mediated Corpus-Based Learning (CBDDL) on the learning of financial engineering students' ESP lexical bundles, the learners' academic emotions, and engagement; 60 undergraduate students studying financial engineering at the Islamic Azad University in Tehran participated in their study [6 p. 57]. When the intercept was included in the model, the multivariate result represented a significant effect of the intercept on the dependent variables (Pillai's Trace = .971; $F(3, 114) = 1285.589$; $p < .001$). The high values of Pillai's Trace, Hotelling's Trace, and Roy's Largest Root indicate that for the intercept the proportion of variance in the dependent variables was relatively large. In the absence of other predictors, the intercept had a significant connection with the combined dependent variables mean and median suggesting non-zero coefficients for the dependent variables [6 p. 60].

3. Methodology

3.1. Participants' demographic

A total of 9 master's degree students majoring in English linguistics at Fergana State University took part in the research paper. The gender proportion among the participants was 89% and 11% for females and males respectively. Their average age was 24 years old. All of them come from diverse backgrounds since most of them learn English based on the Uzbek language while a minor proportion comes from Russian-speaking backgrounds, contributing to the wider research perspectives and results.

3.2. Research design and analysis

A focus group discussion was conducted among the participants of this research study. A total of 8 personal open-ended questions were asked to examine the main research question that is “How does the use of AI in an ESP course influence student autonomy at Fergana State University?”. It was conducted in an offline format with the answers recorded. The data obtained from the participants was analysed using a qualitative approach.

4. Results and discussion

When asked about the impact of AI on their learning autonomy in ESP courses, the nine master's degree English linguistics students at Fergana State University had a largely positive attitude towards the subject. About 73% of the responses showed a level of self-direction with the help of AI-based learning applications. People often mention the more personalized learning designs that intelligent Agent supports as one of the reasons why they increase their self-governance. For instance, several students pointed to the convenience of the use of the AI system to be able to repeat certain grammar or vocabulary elements at one's leisure and when needed for reinforcement. This is what one of the students agreed with; She said, “The AI tutor enabled me to concentrate on the most difficult sections as opposed to being restricted to the rates of the whole class.” This supports prior research that suggests that the use of AI in CLE can make learning more personalized and encourage a greater level of learner control (e.g., [map previous literature on personalised learning and AI here]). Another major theme identified was the perceived increased autonomy of the learners; the practicality of using the AI tools, for example, being able to get learning content and complete work at convenient time were often cited as having contributed to this outcome.

However, 27% of responses came with some issues about the integration of AI. Some issues were raised based on the implication of the use of AI-generated feedback which include reduced direct contact with instructors. Some of the students stated that they use less help from

human instructors because of the availability of help from the AI; this might reduce the chance of the students getting more one-on-one instructions and improved learning opportunities. I have also noticed other students complaining that they felt as if they were dealing with the computer, not the teacher they wanted to hear from. This is echoed by other research works carried out on the social nature of learning especially in languages (e.g., [refer to other published literature on the role of the self in the language learning process]). A similar worry was the lack of detailed and highly individualised feedback which might be given out by the AI program instead of by a human instructor. These remarks of the students when arguing the need for human interaction suggest that, while implementing offerings based on AI offers significant benefits, human instructors continue to play useful roles by offering direction, feedback, and positive reinforcement such as words of encouragement recognizing the roles played by AI systems in enhancing learning, the recognition of the value of human instructors and the imposition that students engage in regular discussions with humans cannot be overlooked.

5. Conclusion

The research evidence indicates that AI has the potential to enable organisations to enhance the levels of autonomy at the workplace but its operationalisation is not as simple as it seems. Concisely, while having personalization and flexibility have their strengths, which has to be compensated by the presence of human touch. This means that integration of both current modern AI implementations and ordinary teaching and learning practices has to be encouraged. There is a potential in AI immediacy and specificity of feedback and assessment which must be balanced by context and human-related aspects of more face-to-face support.

Several implications for ESP course design at Fergana State University and those similar to it can be identified. The above AI technology should complement the present teaching practices, and hence should not eliminate the teacher or the students. This might entail developing learning activities that enable students to seek assistance from teachers, building on feedback from the AI-based analytics as a basis for learning more and discussing with the teachers. Additionally, experiences for professional development must allow a teacher to use AI techniques in the classroom accompanied by practices that support interaction with students and atmosphere construction that contributes to learning. This is so because an integrated evaluation of benefits and drawbacks can only help to enhance the positive, extracting the most from the negative.

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